

Transcript

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Frederik

FN: What is your role and in what capacity do you participate here at the European Negotiation Conference?

CB: Okay, so I have a various role, but let's say my main role is to do research and teaching on frontline negotiation. I'm the founder of the Center of Competence on Humanitarian Negotiation six years ago, and as I was living in Geneva, building an empirical base of practices of humanitarian and other frontline negotiation, I wrote the first manual, CCHN Field Manual on Frontline Negotiation, and building on that, I've been teaching at Harvard University for 25 years and other universities in the world on crisis negotiation, drawing from this, these empirical analysis of practices, conducted over 400 interviews of practitioners.

Based on that in 2022 - 2023, I wanted to explore the potential impact of artificial intelligence on the systematic approach to negotiation and on negotiation practices. So, I entered into a partnership with a team of machine learning specialists at the Harvard School of Engineering and Applied Sciences, and with MIT, and started to develop and validate AI models to assist negotiators. That was the inception of what I'm doing. Now it has evolved, of course, with the technology, but also the preliminary observation. I shifted from technology to the user experience as being more complex. Technology has its linear development, it's taking place. The user experience is still quite vague and entrapped into some of the mismatch between expectations and output. And this is where I'm currently mostly working on developing the new manual that will come out in 2025 on frontline negotiation, but now with AI, and developing of new courses, and a community of practice called frontline associates.

FN: Could you expand a bit what you meant by crisis negotiation?

CB: Yes, crisis negotiation is the negotiation that has high stakes, meaning the issues really matters for the parties, or for third parties, meaning it will have a huge impact on the life, dignity, economy, society of people. It also implies a degree of complexity, dynamic, evolving, with a lot of information coming in and out of the process, multi-stakeholders, which defies the ability of traditional negotiator to deal with this load of information. And the third element is adversarial, meaning that there's a political tension, there's a power imbalance in the negotiation, which makes the resolution of the issue even more difficult, because if there's an emotional load being used and leveraged by the parties in the negotiation, that's what is crisis negotiation.

FN: I have talked to a person from the french national police, and he negotiated in what he would call crisis negotiations, so terrorism, kidnapping, and the like. I asked him, how would he negotiate from a position of less power, and he answered: "we're the police, we're always in the position of power." And I found that very interesting, this is the perception of somebody who is always in charge and has more resources. Does

48 this constitute a crisis negotiation?
49 And thinking about the complexity and the emotion of topics we are
50 negotiating in the US and Europe, it seems there are similar problems on
51 the social side, from migration, power struggles to fragmented power
52 systems in the government. Looking at these complex topics, what do you
53 think has the greatest impact on the way we negotiate?

54 **CB:** Okay, let's say my approach to negotiation is much closer to
55 behaviouralist vision, in the sense that it's a human experience. I do
56 emphasize negotiation as being a human-led process, and what defines a
57 crisis is a situation that goes beyond the ability of these particular
58 humans to deal with it. So, is it because of the stakes?

59 Negotiating a hostage crisis is particularly overwhelming for people who
60 are not trained and have experience, because the life of someone is at
61 stake, or several people, but because of complexity, create a crisis, or
62 cognitive abilities are limited because of time, resources, or expertise,
63 or ultimately adversity, adversarial relationship, very hostile,
64 intimidating negotiation, as we've seen around Trump, the way the adversity
65 is being created to overwhelm the counterpart. So that's what defines the
66 crisis. Now you could be having a crisis negotiation with your
67 mother-in-law, or you would have a crisis negotiation with Vladimir Putin,
68 but it's still from the human perspective. Now there are issues which
69 belong to political crisis, which belong to a labor dispute, that is
70 brought in crisis with Air France, or whatever. These are economic, social,
71 labor crisis, but not necessarily a negotiation crisis.
72 So the very experienced labor dispute negotiators will work on, let's say,
73 a labor dispute with SNCF, or with Air France, that's not a crisis. It's
74 all mapped out, they understand the situation, the stakes are clear, the
75 stakeholder, the negotiator, and it's the same with the policemen you
76 mentioned.

77 There's not 50 ways a hostage negotiation will go, it's maybe 8 or 12, and
78 because they are in the police, they've been exposed to these 12 ways many
79 times. So, for them, they are not in crisis. In fact, in machine language
80 mode, we say higher the biases, the narrower the variance. And also, the
81 situation can have very high biases, biases in terms of tension, complexity,
82 stakes, but the higher they are, the narrower the variance of
83 possibilities. This is a very striking point, if you move into AI thinking,
84 that explains why these policemen look very confident, because there's not
85 the 65th way hostage negotiations going to go, it doesn't exist, and
86 they've been scoping out continuously the 12 ways a hostage negotiation
87 will go. That doesn't mean they don't improvise, but it's very narrow.

88 **FN:** Do I understand it right, that the complexity is not only the
89 complexity of the relation between the negotiators, or the amount of
90 information, but also the complexity of outcomes that are possible?

91 **CB:** Yes, but as I said, the higher the biases, the narrower the complexity
92 of the outcomes, and this is really a revelation. Once you start to think
93 about complexity in negotiation, you see, if you have a low bias, for
94 example, you're negotiating in a neighbourhood on what to do with the park,
95 then you have tons of possibilities and relationships going on within the
96 neighbourhood, with the shops, and the school, and the mayor, and so on.
97 It's highly complex, but it's about a park, so low stakes, probably not
98 very high adversity, and therefore, the possible outcomes are very large,

99 but the negotiation is not a crisis negotiation, it may be highly complex,
100 but in fact, whatever the outcome is going to be, they will be happy with.
101 The type of pressure on the negotiator, or the degree of professionalism
102 expected, is quite different, because the emotional overload is not there,
103 the adversity is not there, and the stakes are not that high.

104 **FN:** It's also these three concepts of adversity, stakes, and complexity,
105 that you would say may define how challenging a negotiation could be?

106 **CB:** Yes.

107 **FN:** Talking about demanding negotiations, have you yourself, or have you
108 accompanied someone in a very demanding negotiation, where you noticed that
109 this is like a really complicated and difficult subject, and what were the
110 aspects that brought these negotiations to a positive or negative outcome?

111 **CB:** I personally, I was a frontline negotiator for about 15 years of my
112 life, or maybe 20 across my career, mostly with the ICRC and the United
113 Nations, at different level of field, and then at strategic level. I have
114 been a strategic advisor to the president of the ICRC for 10 years. I
115 personally conducted negotiations, and these reflections are also out of my
116 own practice of seeing the high stakes in humanitarian negotiation,
117 frontline complexity. Multi-stakeholder is extremely dynamic environment,
118 and adversarial to the sky. To a large extent, this adversity is also an
119 engine, because it links to power imbalance. So more adversarial the
120 negotiation is, the more potential you have to build trust precisely
121 dealing with adversity, that is building trust and legitimacy, and getting
122 a positive output.

123 However, and this drew my interest into negotiation practices, because what
124 I saw in the humanitarian field in particular, but security negotiation in
125 general, these negotiations are being seen as highly personal, depends on
126 the negotiator, x, y, z, won't negotiate the same way. And confidential, so
127 you don't know really what was negotiated and how, mostly how, and
128 contextual, you negotiate in Turkey in a certain way, in Russia in another,
129 and this appreciation of personal, confidential, and contextual doesn't fit
130 empirical observation, meaning a great negotiator is a great negotiator
131 everywhere. If you have a very experienced negotiator in Zimbabwe, will he
132 be a great negotiator in Myanmar? Actually, yes, and this is fascinating,
133 and this is why I started doing these interviews of frontline negotiators,
134 and particularly the one I'm thinking about here is a Zimbabwean
135 professional working in Chitwan in Myanmar for WFP. He is one of the best
136 negotiators I've ever seen, because he has an understanding of how military
137 sectarian parties operate, and to negotiate in Myanmar is exactly what you
138 need to have, that many negotiators don't have, so the experience and
139 practices can be transposed, so context is not a good driver, then personal
140 experience can also be transposed.

141 [shot interruption my Kirk Kinell entering the room]

142 **CB:** But to come back to the point, person, you can learn a lot by sharing
143 and observing another negotiator, you can transpose by context, you can
144 transpose by person, and the confidentiality. Actually, negotiators cannot
145 stop talking about their experience, I mean, what is confidential is a date,
146 time, location, people, not to be misused by intelligence service or
147 whatnot, but they're very approachable, and like you I recorded hundreds of

148 hours of interviews with people like Kirk, so it means there are practices,
149 it's not Tom, Dick and Harry and Julie the negotiators, it's practices that
150 can be transposed out of context, transposed out of people, and transposed
151 out of their particular constraints of confidentiality, and that is the
152 basis of what a craft is. The *métier* of negotiator, if you can capture
153 enough of it, and with a critical mass of this knowledge you create a craft,
154 and I think the craft of negotiator has not been created yet, it's coming
155 about. The center of competence is one step in that direction, the creation
156 of manuals, but again, you still have people who teach or train on
157 negotiation as an extrapolation of their own personality, Eric Lempereur
158 [maybe Alain Lempereur?], it's a show of virtuosis, but you're not Eric
159 Lempereur, you're not, you know, what's his name, the guy on YouTube? Chris
160 Voss, yes, they are persona, you know, you cannot replicate persona, you
161 look silly if you try to be Chris Voss, I mean, this is all about jaws and
162 muscles, and you know, it's YouTube culture but it's not expertise. My goal
163 with the CCHM, with this manual, and now with AI, is how to capture
164 expertise, to depersonalize, decontextualize, and make it more accessible.

165 **FN:** Would you say that there's a – in lack of a better word – a holistic
166 approach to negotiation that can be transcribed into different aspects?

167 **CB:** Yes, it's a *métier*. In English the word "craft", as architects,
168 engineers, you may have. It's not a science, it is on the complex side, it
169 is about human relationship, but it's about difficult human relationship,
170 and then we're back to high biases, low variance. Difficult relationships
171 are something you can learn, because there's a low variance, as compared to
172 easy relationship, huge variance, you can learn by doing, what are you
173 learning actually, because it's so unpredictable what's going to happen,
174 but difficult relationships are highly predictable, more difficult but more
175 predictable.

176 **FN:** From what you found out until now, in a short summary, what would you
177 say makes a great negotiator, what is the craft?

178 **CB:** I think the craft is made of one experience with difficult
179 relationships, and when I say experience, not only learning by doing, but
180 learn by sharing, observing, reflecting. When I'm dealing with students
181 learning negotiation, I say find yourself a mentor, find yourself a great
182 negotiator, and simply shadow the person, you'll learn so much. So,
183 learning by doing, sharing, and reflecting is the bedrock, as you have
184 apprenticeship in other craft, this is how knowledge is transmitted to a
185 large extent, not in university courses, and people pay a lot of money for
186 executive training on negotiation. But this is abstract conceptual ideas,
187 it's not craft. It's framing, is all conceptual frame. But you may have
188 gone all the courses it doesn't make you a negotiator, right?

189 The second part is inherent skills about empathy, compassion, and a great
190 ability to disembodify yourself in negotiation, as not carrying your own set
191 of values and norms and experience, but focusing on the ability to build
192 bridges with the counterpart, in whatever situation you're in. You
193 recognize these great negotiators, because they are mirrors, like Kirk is
194 one. You sit in front of them, and you see yourself, the way they behave,
195 the non-verbal language, the way they talk, there's something mirroring you
196 as a natural. But it's not natural, it's learned, but, and it is
197 frustrating, when I see someone doing it, I say, please stop it, I'm
198 beating myself. I'm talking about crisis negotiators, you know, when you

199 have 15 seconds to establish: is it going to work or not? This is a set of
200 skills that you recognize with great negotiators.

201 **FN:** I like this point, I started to play around with different methods of
202 teaching, because I noticed that explaining it abstractly had no impact.
203 People felt intelligent afterwards, but I did not see it implemented. From
204 your perspective, what would be the biggest gap you see at the moment
205 between practitioners, researchers, and third parties of the civil society
206 in this sphere of negotiation?

207 **CB:** I think civil society's mission is not to negotiate, and it's a bit
208 difficult to train NGO practitioners to negotiation, because for them
209 negotiation is an extension of advocacy, they do not understand it's about
210 compromise. And it has a cost, the mission of civil society is not to cut
211 deals on their core values, it's to put pressure. Negotiators cut deals,
212 not NGOs, MSF is not there, I mean, as an operator, yes, I'm sorry, but for
213 example Amnesty International is not there to cut deals, Human Rights First
214 is not there to cut deals. If you go back to the people, people that enter
215 into humanitarian activities, or human rights, or climate, they come with
216 an agenda, their personal commitment. It takes a while before they
217 understand that, if you want to negotiate, it needs to stay outside the
218 room, negotiation is not about convincing the other side of anything, and
219 that is a big obstacle for civil society entering into the negotiation.
220 Their core mission is to promote a civil society agenda, negotiation is
221 about cutting a deal, make a compromise, establishing a relationship, trust,
222 and legitimacy in that personal interaction. It's not the role of civil
223 society, it's the role of negotiators to do that.

224 So, the main liability of civil society organization, professionals and
225 practitioners is their belief system. In the negotiation circle, there's no
226 belief system, except we are creating safe space for having a dialogue. For
227 researchers and then I would put educators, is to bring their concept into
228 negotiation practice, much more deductive approach, through modelling. I
229 mean you have the Harvard way, you have the many other ways, which have
230 never been grounded in practice, because there was no empirical research
231 behind it. "Getting to yes", it's not a practice-based theory, it's a
232 vision of Robert Fisher and Bill Ury, which is impressive in its
233 practicality and rational interest, transactional negotiation, but this is
234 it. It's a rational model. So, because it created so much followers, you
235 find it mirrored in practice, but it's not practice-based, it's not an
236 inductive model. It's sometimes caught up into its own success, because it
237 says, practice is BATNA, is interest-based. But if you going to negotiate
238 in Afghanistan or Russia or China, forget about it. It's not the Harvard
239 model. People are caught off guard, because suddenly hostility arise, or
240 the complexity is overwhelming.

241 Interestingly, the Harvard model is very vulnerable to AI, because it is so
242 rational, you can put "Getting to yes", and all the concepts and theories
243 and case book into a model in three minutes flat, and that's it. You no
244 longer need action, because the model will tell you, based on statistical
245 probability, what you should be doing next, way better than spending seven
246 thousand dollars and learning about the about this concept, you see what I
247 mean? Because it's so rational-based, reasoning-based, as compared to
248 spending 10 years in Myanmar to figure out how does the Zimbabwean guy
249 manage to negotiate with the colonel.

250 **FN:** So, this concept established itself in its practice by being so popular,
251 but other areas of the planet negotiate differently, and have like
252 different concepts, ideas behind the negotiation. What would you say,
253 especially from your more American perspective, what is something peculiar
254 about how the Europeans negotiate?

255 **CB:** Well, first of all, I don't think I'm an American perspective per se.
256 I've spent most of my professional life in Europe and trained in Geneva,
257 also trained in the U.S. and teaching in the U.S., but I don't see myself
258 part of the U.S. way of negotiating, which is very much interest-based
259 negotiation, power negotiation, power-driven negotiation, which some
260 Europeans are adopting. Many in the private sector being Egger Philips, or
261 Agence des Negociateurs in Paris, they are all spin-offs of U.S. way of
262 negotiating. If we talk private sector, most of the private sector
263 negotiation have been colonized by the Harvard way, because they've been
264 trained. So, I don't think this distinction between the two is such a
265 geographic point, but there is evidently a distinction.

266 First in terms of the sense of ethics, ethos, and responsibility in Europe
267 is very strong. Negotiators are not in this free zone, there is layers of
268 norms that they should abide to, that you do not have necessarily in a,
269 let's say, more western, purely rational model, but this rational model is
270 again in China, Australia, everywhere. This is why the European nature of
271 it is – I think – not the right configuration. I think it's the notion of
272 responsible negotiation versus purely interest-based negotiation. And then
273 you have that tension everywhere, you have it around the autochthonous
274 rights, indigenous rights in Canada, are we are negotiating purely on
275 interest-based, or do we consider that we as negotiators have a mission to
276 protect diversity, for example, or the environment? This layering of norms
277 into the negotiation room is a key feature of a more positivist approach to
278 law, norms, where we don't exist as free agents, as a political philosophy,
279 but we are social actors with responsibilities and ethos.

280 You see that reflection on negotiation heavily, but with a certain sarcasm
281 of one who says: "Of course, you need to negotiate." And the other says:
282 "oh no, we look like nuns." Like this conference started with this young
283 generation stating the non-negotiable. Okay, good, thank you very much.
284 This is the European opening to a conference on negotiation. It is purely
285 European in that sense, where positivist law says, no, we don't negotiate
286 everything. And there's a sense of disarray of Europeans in front of
287 negotiation, not because of techniques and tools they don't understand, but
288 simply it is not possible to negotiate the matter, it is not possible. At a
289 European conference on negotiation, you will need to have the "petite
290 chorale" showing up and saying, but you remember there are things you don't
291 negotiate. This is unthinkable in the US, this is absent, you know, it's
292 kind of a little insider.

293 **FN:** This is a fascinating perspective, and I feel like especially
294 humanitarian negotiations I experienced situations that were ethically and
295 morally ambivalent. But at the same time, you need to negotiate it, you
296 need to find a solution for all of this, so you put the Pandora's box to
297 the back, discussing the philosophical question later, but now you focus on
298 the stakes at hand.

299 **CB:** But you see, this is not a negotiation issue, it's a positivist issue.
300 It's that there's a notion that you have natural laws, you have

301 constitutional laws, international laws, you have moralistic norms, and you
302 don't have a critical distance vis-a-vis that about the colonial nature of
303 these norms, about the power relationships of European nations. This whole
304 layer of assumptions that people learn. But this is critical thinking,
305 they don't have critical thinking in humanitarian sphere, but any of the
306 colonial nature of the enterprise, which once you get a bit away from it,
307 then it all falls apart. Especially as humanitarian on the front line, of
308 course, you negotiate your mother, if it's going to give you a return on
309 anything. I would have negotiated the exchange of weapons, if there's a
310 humanitarian benefit. But this is simply inconceivable in the [European]
311 nature. I mean, I see courses on negotiation in Geneva, they all start by
312 the non-negotiable. Amazing, thank you very much.

313 Okay, I mean, really, it's like a reinforcement of beliefs. You're allowed
314 to talk about negotiation only if you reinforce the belief about what the
315 non-negotiable is. This is what happened here at the opening ceremony,
316 which is not a surprise for me. It's a given. You go to Europe, you're
317 going to get served. Like when I teach AI, I will always get someone says,
318 what about the carbon footprint of AI? I say, yeah, good. Okay, I mean,
319 it's a given. There's a young generation who's so confused about the
320 environment that they cling on concerns and arguments that are beside the
321 point. The carbon footprint of them going to Barcelona to buy a pair of
322 shoes is 10,000 times what they will ever use of AI in their whole life and
323 their cousins. So, that you don't question. Their carbon footprint of going
324 to a discotheque or whatever, is immensely more important than their use of
325 AI. But their concern about us using AI in climate negotiation is
326 moralistic. How can you use AI in a climate convention?
327 Well, you know, 100,000 people going to Baku, they get planes. If we can
328 get 5,000 less that pays for AI for the next three generations. The
329 relative nature of the concern is absent, and I think this is typically a
330 defensive measure on complexity. Let's simplify things here. This carbon
331 footprint of using your AI, but the fact that you're using a phone that
332 comes from way more carbon than your use of AI. That's complex. So, this
333 oversimplification, this inability to open a free space, this free space is
334 where critical thinking starts. But it starts with confusion. If you're not
335 confused, you cannot think critically.

336 **FN:** ... and come up with new ideas.

337 **CB:** Yeah, this as humanitarian in a negotiation, I think it's a basic point.
338 Let's say somebody wants to get to engage in human negotiation, they
339 should start to be confused about their own values.

340 **FN:** I really like to have this new spin on my own confusion at times. You
341 have it more positively framed. Until now, I always had this concept of
342 vertigo in my head. I'm spinning, now this stuff doesn't make sense. Calm
343 down and work from there.

344 **CB:** It's like a religious belief is articulated around the doubt. Well, I
345 think humanitarian beliefs should be articulated around profound critical
346 thinking about your project.

347 **FN:** That brings me nicely to the next question. What do you think is a key
348 skill that today's negotiators should learn or that's something that the
349 next generation should work out and get taught or experience themselves?
350 What is this key skill?

351 **CB:** Okay, well, then I'll shift to really my platform. Negotiators with AI
352 will replace negotiators without AI. This is beyond doubt. So, an AI as a
353 modus operandi, not as a technology. AI as a world of opportunities and
354 risk, not an app. It's a paradigmatic shift that is so transformative that
355 negotiators who want to operate from whatever field, humanitarian to
356 commercial, need to understand that the complexity and adversity and
357 probably stakes because of the issues is going to skyrocket. Without AI,
358 you're done. You can still negotiate with your mother and all. Anything
359 beyond the personal will be AI-driven.

360 **FN:** So understanding how to use that, how to implement that and how to use
361 it as you do it, not as an automation, but as a reflection of what you do?

362 **CB:** Yes, as a co-design capability. It's so foundational that it's hard to
363 imagine. You know, people say it about creation of the internet. Oh, I went
364 through the creation of the internet. I saw the professional impact, which
365 was profound in terms of how institutions work, how people work,
366 communicate, network, both positive and a lot negative, right? How they
367 date. It's profound. But I think AI is many times more than that. Because
368 of our inability to process what the AI is doing. To move from fax to email,
369 you can get it, right? To move from let's say dictionary to Wikipedia, you
370 can get that. But to move from thinking without AI, with AI you can't. And
371 one of the big difficulties is people are still functioning as if, what I
372 call the semiotic trap. It's still functioning as AI has meaning. When they
373 do a summary of text on an AI model, they think that the AI model
374 understands the text. It doesn't. But the semiotic projection is so
375 entrenched into our understanding of language that we don't know how to
376 operate with AI. So, email is a projection of facts, but AI is not a
377 projection of human thinking.

378 I think the equivalent in terms of impact is more the deployment of radio
379 in the 1920s on the countryside. When the radio came into villages there
380 were profound changes of relationship in life and economy and society and
381 music and art. Because suddenly, why play music when you can simply turn
382 your things on? But you never play music by yourself. You always played it
383 on every Saturday with your neighbour. There was society, all the dating
384 life was linked to these little festivals and whatnot. Radio stopped
385 everything. Radio had a profound change on society. But also, positive
386 change about voting rights for women, about change of culture. That's
387 paradigm shift. It's not technological evolution. I think that's where AI
388 is just starting.

389 To go back to your question, negotiators – especially the young generation
390 – who want to learn how to negotiate, either they do it in the old way, as
391 we've been talking, or they say, well, I'm going to ask the AI mode how to
392 negotiate. The AI model is going to tell you how to negotiate. It's going
393 to tell you everything. It will saturate you with knowledge how to
394 negotiate in whatever circumstances, in whatever language you want. Except
395 it doesn't know how to negotiate. But it's so much effective, cheaper, and
396 accessible, especially you talk about the global south. You know that we
397 work with the delegation of Mali at the COP. Is this AI really helpful?
398 Delegation of Mali can rely on AI to negotiate 10 times, 20, 100 times
399 better than they do without. Because it gives them the power of analysis,
400 and can write that famous letter to China in seconds. And you don't need to
401 go through workshops on how to make an argument, how to think, and how to
402 blah blah blah blah. Put it on the AI. It will be more effective. Imagine,

403 even with the intellectual gap, educational gap, turn on the machine, and
404 you become the voice of an agent. An AI agent. So, the risk associated to
405 the use of AI in negotiation outweighed many times the benefit. Yes. Many
406 times.

407 So, but as with the radio, it's going to happen. It's not going to say:
408 "Radio is not coming in my village." It is coming. So, how do we actually
409 approach AI in negotiation? And how should we approach it? How should we
410 train and encourage people to work with AI? It's not by, as we saw in some
411 of the workshops here, oh, let's then practice the effectiveness model. The
412 effectiveness is a trap. I tell that to my student at Harvard, your brain
413 is shrinking each time you ask the model a question. Because first, you're
414 a young professional. Of course, the model knows better. But creating this
415 dependence as an editor of the journal, you can use a model, of course, but
416 then you're no longer the editor of the journal. The model is. And it's not
417 going to build the ability to edit. It's going to build the ability to use
418 a model to edit. So, the point here is that we need to escape this
419 efficiency. Start to work in co-design, developing new narrative, new way
420 of thinking. And that, these tools, methods, and courses don't exist. They
421 don't yet.

422 And the models, commercially produced, are all driven you to be more and
423 more dependent on it. Linking to Word, Teams, Google Drive. They're going
424 to write your own LinkedIn posts. I mean, they become central and effective
425 tools. And you become dumber and dumber. So, negotiators of tomorrow won't
426 be there. Negotiating with AI, most of the negotiator won't be negotiator
427 by then. I say negotiator with AI will replace negotiator without AI. But
428 AI will replace many of these negotiators anyway. So, these negotiators
429 won't be negotiating anywhere, anytime soon. AI will disable negotiators
430 who have fallen to the effectiveness trap. It's rather negotiators that
431 know how to deal with AI in the creative, critical way, will be super
432 negotiators. That is the stake. But that, the Mali delegation is not going
433 to make it. The German delegation may. So, the digital gap is going to
434 become enormous.

435 And a point too, it's the semantic feedback loop. You ask a model to
436 produce a speech, even half of it. The speech, exposition, policy papers,
437 article, whatever you ask the model to produce. There's what we call the
438 phantom meaning. Because as semiotic, you think there's meaning behind it.
439 But this is a probabilistic model. It doesn't produce meaning. It produces
440 statistical inference of the next word. There's no meaning. If you write an
441 article on what I'm saying with an AI model, it simply conjugates words
442 probabilistic. There's no meaning behind it. The model doesn't understand
443 anything I'm saying. It's simply predicting the next word, based on
444 articles I produce myself or whatnot. That could be an article. Yeah, but
445 it has no meaning. You think it has, but it doesn't. Then the reader says,
446 oh, make a summary. Oh, it's a too long article. I don't have time and put
447 that AI produced material into an AI model, which doesn't know the meaning,
448 doesn't care about meaning. It would simply process a summary or an
449 analysis based on probabilistic inference. And you think it has captured
450 the meaning that anyway didn't exist in the first place. And the you have
451 what we call the semantic feedback loop.

452 Now this semantic feedback, we are bound to get into it. We have already in
453 university where GPT papers are being corrected by GPT correctors, then you
454 have that loop. First, we're out of it. Human out of the loop, like in

455 these autonomous weapons. But all the biases, inherent inclinations of the
456 database that are not meaning, they're simply patterns, accelerate. So,
457 you're talking about the western perspective, the global north perspective,
458 the language inclination. If your text is in Kyrgyz, it's going to simply
459 swirl down into meaninglessness. If it's in English, it will have a certain
460 panache. This loop, because this article, this summary, of course, will
461 inform another article, which will also be produced with AI assistance and
462 then feedback again into the loop. So, our intellectual, cognitive,
463 creative contribution becomes narrower and narrower.

464 People imagine replacement as being the robot showing up and all the
465 anthropomorphism associated to it. No, the replacement is this thinning of
466 human contribution. Because, I mean, you'll be using AI for this interview
467 and somebody's going to be using AI to edit this into an article and
468 somebody will be using AI making a summary of it and then that's it. The
469 loop is there. And I think that negotiators who don't see that loop,
470 they're gone. It's a matter of the generation of thinning of many of the
471 most technocratic, bureaucratic, institutional, and I would say with the
472 inclination of positivist thinking, where you say there are certain things
473 we don't criticize. This is protocol. This is pure butter from the AI model.
474 Of course, you want to have the human internal perspective on x, y, z?
475 I'll write it for you! You want to have the human rights, gender,
476 environmentalist perspective on x? I'll write it better than you could ever
477 do. Because these are patterns. And then the loop starts. And finally, what
478 is your contribution as a believer into humanitarian, climate, human rights
479 values? It's irrelevant because it has been patternized there.

480 **FN:** It reminds me a bit of this anthropocentric view of nature where you
481 see the whatever nature provides as a function for you. It's raining so we
482 can have water. The flowers are nice because we can enjoy them. And then
483 you start to put a meaning into something that just doesn't have it.

484 **CB:** Yeah. You talk to your toaster in the morning. This is this part. You
485 think your dog is really having an emotion, but in fact he's hungry. It's
486 true. And then the policies and marketing of these models are all playing
487 on it. Each time a model tells you great question, I want to shoot my
488 computer. Because this is not true. This is a hook. It wants to please you,
489 to make you think you're smart. It's always a great question. Even if it
490 says, what a bad question. How stupid are you? Actually, your question
491 should have been XYZ. Or it should be asking you the question. Tell me what
492 you think shouldn't be that and then I'll tell you if you're right. Or if
493 it's based on my patterns. So, it doesn't work on deviance. It simply
494 strengthens, as you embark into the loop and strengthen the gravitational
495 force toward that established pattern.

496 **FN:** This is my last question and usually the most difficult question for
497 people to answer and I would I'm super happy if this is pertaining to AI,
498 but also to broaden the concept of negotiation in itself. What piece of
499 media would you recommend people interested from music, theatre, books,
500 movies, whatever kind of media to people who are interested in negotiation
501 to consume? Would it be something that pops up in your mind where you're
502 like, oh, you should have seen that, you should read that?

503 **CB:** The diplomat. The movie. It's a French translated, but it's a French
504 movie with this actor that is still all over the place, but it's a
505 production of a theatre play. It's a story of a Swedish consular in the

506 last days of Paris occupation, which is based on true facts, where he's
507 trying to convince the SS commander, Patton, who has mined the bombs in all
508 the cultural landmarks of Patton. So, when the Germans would withdraw, the
509 Louvre would go into pieces and everything. And he has this dialogue for a
510 few days with this person. These two are about, it's a, it's a theatre play,
511 you know, but it's in a movie called The Diplomat. It's extraordinary. It
512 blew my mind.

513 As a rhetorical point, the tone of it. But as I said, to sit beside, to
514 shadow a negotiator, some artists movies, which I say is different from,
515 you know, Alain Lempereur is in love with Nanjing siege negotiation, but
516 this is, this is épopée, this is like historical. Like this holy
517 half-Jesus-Christ negotiator, who convinced don't kill the children, the
518 type of the Jewish ghetto stories and so on. In this darkness of genocide
519 and holocaust, we all need to find the angels, right? So Joe Globe[??], who
520 was running the manufacturer where some Jews were working, saved lives of
521 50 people and that makes him a great negotiator. No, it's our fear of
522 darkness that made these people great. And they manage as they should. I'm
523 not diminishing their moralistic actions and more important, their courage.
524 But you cannot transpose that because we fortunately don't live currently
525 through these circumstances. And if we would, angels like this would appear,
526 not because they're great negotiators, because they have huge balls and
527 many die. Only those who survive will be heard about and they're part of
528 the Holocaust memorial and so on. So, but that is not modelling what
529 negotiations should be. It's, it's more like sacred.

530 No, I think the humble, the very discreet, equally courageous, although
531 their life may not be as much at that risk, who, and many of those I
532 interviewed were these people and these interviews stay with me as their
533 key characteristic is humbleness. They're not even in the history book,
534 right? But they knew how to do it. What was your question again?

535 **FN:** It was the piece of media that the people should consume?

536 **CB:** Yes, yes, yes. So, diplomat is accessible. It's a, it's a bit tedious,
537 because it's two actors talking in a room, you know.

538 **FN:** I exactly know what I'm going to watch once I'm back here from Paris.
539 That sounds amazing. Yes, yes. All right. That will conclude our interview.
540 If there's a talking point that you were like, oh, you missed something
541 here or there's something I noticed and you didn't ask, is there anything
542 that you would like to add?

543 **CB:** It's the notion of a community. It's also, as you're working around
544 your journal, it is the commitment of a community for something. And for
545 improving the practice. So, the commitment is toward a practice that
546 doesn't exist yet. It's normative. It's a vision. It's an ideal. And in
547 everything we've been talking is like whole scientific, how people
548 negotiate and what they should be doing still as individuals, right? But
549 the quality of the craft is linked to this commitment. And this is more
550 than a footnote. It is a community of practice and I wrote about community
551 of practice. In negotiation it is intention. Because, the persona of
552 negotiators is very "lonely wolf". Like Kirk, we just saw and these super
553 negotiators. They're always self-reliant and alone which doesn't correspond
554 to empirical studies. Great negotiators always operating in teams. They are
555 at times invisible. The real N1, N2 negotiators are not actually the head

556 of negotiation. The experienced negotiators, although they were young N1,
557 N2 at the negotiation table, tend not to be there anymore because they need
558 a critical space to guide the negotiation.

559 Then they know each other like crazy, like Kirk comes in, we hug. So, this
560 community is a critical aspect of the craft. And for the young generation
561 who all want to be mission impossible type of negotiators. Well, it's an
562 illusion. They need to give up. It's like a scout in the military sense.
563 These lone people who go around. No, scout is part of scoutism, the
564 movement scout, a group of people. This is a set of values and norms and
565 way of operating and encouraging ourselves with badges and whatnot and
566 start too young and end up 50 years old people and say you're still in a
567 scout. This community is what is behind great negotiators. If you're not in
568 it, you won't be a great negotiator because you don't have that sharing and
569 reflection um model going on continuously. And these people are so
570 reluctant with everything with AI, not that they're not using it. They're
571 all using it. But they understand that this AI is not what negotiation is
572 all about. Negotiation is about my connection to Kirk, to this one, to this
573 one. And I think this is an important element as you look into into
574 developing the craft.

575 **FN:** I think this is an amazing conclusion, especially because it supports
576 what we're doing with the journal. I'm very happy about this. Thank you so
577 much. That was really fascinating. That was a lot of fun.